

LOVE AND DEATH THEMES IN THE POETRY OF
MUHAMMAD YUSUF

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Abstract: This article talks about the life and work of the Uzbek poet Muhammad Yusuf, shows that he is not only a singer of the motherland, but also a singer of love, and how effectively he interprets the themes of love and death in his poems

Keywords: Love, death, lyrical pictures, sorrow, pain, worries, joy, affection, thoughts.

Muhammad Yusuf, the national poet of Uzbekistan, the creator of the nation's pride, who has a deep place in the hearts of the people through his simple and perfect works, was born on April 26, 1954 in the village of Qovunchi, Marhamat district, Andijan province, in a farmer's family. He was interested in literature since childhood, so, after finishing high school, in 1978 he graduated from the Institute of Russian Language and Literature (now Uzbekistan State University of World Languages)

Throughout his short life, Muhammad Yusuf composed a large number of poems, and these poems gained popularity because they were clear, simple, and pure, and they effectively conveyed the national song, the sorrow of love, the pain of separation, and the dreams of death. His creative works such as “Familiar Poplars” (1985), “I Have a Say to the Nightingale” (1987), “Prayer” (1988), “Sleeping Girl” (1989), “Gods of Halima” (1989), “Ship of Love” (1990), “A Friend in My Heart” (1991), “There is a lot of unfaithfulness” (1991), “Male deer” (1992), “I will take you to heaven” (1998) brought him success and fame.

In 1989, Muhammad Yusuf was awarded the prize of the Republican Youth Organization for his poetry collection "Sleeping Girl". In 1998, he was awarded the title of "People's Poet of Uzbekistan".

In his poems Mukhammad Yusuf highlighted the simple truths he saw in life and expressed the poetry and poems in his poem “I didn’t stop doing what I knew” like this:

Quvroq bo’l deyshdi. Yolg’on ham kerak,
Jindak xushomad ham, quloq solmadim.
Oqni oppoq ko’rdim, qorani – qora
Men o’z bilganimdan qolmadim....
They said me to be more cunning,
To lie, to praise, but I didn’t care.
I saw white as white, the black as black,
I didn’t stop doing what I know and share.....

Today, we'll discuss how Muhammad Yusuf interprets love and death in his poetry. We'll also attempt to become familiar with the poet's deft imagery and feel his anguish and agony.

The theme of love has been one of Muhammad Yusuf's work's well-polished pillars. According to famous philosophers, although love is an old concept, each person rediscovers and renews it. Love-themed poems help the poet write more fluidly, turn an abstract emotion into something concrete, and introduce the idea of feeling small. If there is a place for expression, Muhammad's style finds a special method to portray the sorrows of love, the pains of separation, and loyalty through lyrical pictures and unexpected features. Let’s take a look at the following poem “The sound of love”:

SEVGI SADOSI

Gulim, mehr ko’zda degani yolg’on,
Mening dilimda hech o’chmas yolqinsiz,
Qancha ko’rishmasak shuncha qadrdon,
Qancha olis bo’lsak, shuncha yaqinsiz.

Devona oshiqman, men bir devona,
Ayting sizdan bo'lak kimim bor yana.
Siz yo'q chog'imdagi dunyom begona,
Siz yo'q bog'imdagi gullar yoqimsiz.

Here, the poet expresses to his loved one that he cannot forget her no matter how far or how long they are apart, and that without her, everything is odd and the flowers in the gardens are disagreeable. No one else is so precious to him, and she drives him mad.

In his another poem Muhammad Yusuf defines love in his poetry "Love is..." and uses simple language to convey his thoughts, feelings, and affection for his beloved. He writes that he adores his lover's sad and terrified eyes, and that seeing her thin hands and freckled face even once a day brings him immense joy.

SEVGI BU...

Sevmoq bu
Kechirmoq degani asli,
Toki bu dunyoda quyosh bor, gul bor.
Yalpizlar gullagan shu bahor fasli,
Sodiq hamdam bo'lgin sen menga, dilbar.
Sevmoq bu o'zingni anglamoq asli,
Toki zamin aro quyosh bor, gul bor.
Rayhonga ko'milgan shu bahor fasli,
Sadoqatli yor bol sen menga, dilbar.
Sevgilim, men seni sevaman, tamom,
G'amgin ko'zing, hadik to'la ko'zingni.
Sevmoq, bu kunda bir ko'rmoq baxtidir
Ozg'in qo'llaringni, sepkil yuzingni...

The issue of death is also skillfully interpreted in Muhammad Yusuf's writings, as is the theme of love. His works are full of melodies and words that touch the heart, and everybody who reads one of these poems will unavoidably recall, think about, and feel death for a moment. Let`s read his poetry "Worry":

XAVOTIR

Qo`rqaman, ertaga men o`lib ketsam,
Yotar bo`lsam qumga botib ko`zlarim,
Konglimni ko`chkiday bosadi bir g`am –
Yig`lashni ham bilmas mening qizlarim...
Ular yosh. O`limdan qo`rqaman yomon,
Chunki, dardiga hech quloq solmadim.
Qabrimning ustida yig`lasin debon,
Qizlarim ko`z yoshin asray olmadim!

He asserts in his poetry "Worry" that even if he passes away tomorrow with his eyes buried in the sand, his heart will be broken since his daughters are unable to grieve.

He paints this scenario because he thinks his girls are too young to understand it and he doesn't want them to weep over his grave since he didn't save them from terrible and unhappy times. He believes that the difficult times his girls have experienced in life are enough. In addition, he says he is extremely terrified of dying and all his worries are about his daughters`s future without their father.

In another poem titled "My Pain," Muhammad Yusuf bid his mother farewell and expressed his readiness to pass away. He claimed that death is also like a journey as well, that he would not be cured of his disease, that the light in his eyes was dimming, and that he had given up hope for the future.

MENING DARDIM

Tuzalmaydi dardim mening,
O'lsam kerak.
Tuproq bilan og'a-ini
Bo'lsam kerak.
O'lim nima?Bu ham bitta
Sayr, Ona.
O'g'ling qaro yerga ketdi
Xayr ona....
Tuzalmas bu dardim mening,
Umidim yo'q.
Xira shamdek ko'zlarimda
So'nmoqda cho'g'.
Cho'g' nimadir? Cho'g' ham tutab,
Kul bo'ladi.
Inson bir kun o'z mayliga
Qul bo'ladi...
Yuragimni tamom qildim,
Yig'layverib.
Huzurimda ajal turar,
Qoshin kerib.
Men hayotda o'limga tik
Boqib o'sdim...
Qani menga atalgan joy,
Ketdik, do'stim!

He has depicted such straightforward, relatable, and true circumstances as he has personally encountered ,that they push the reader to empathize with the issue by engaging with the poetry.

Every phrase Muhammad Yusuf used and every occasion in his life was poetry. Like a bird fluttering its wings in the sky, it appeared as though he had led a very light and happy life. The poet, however, died at a young age, the creative process was saved in its poems... Muhammad Yusuf died of a heart attack on July 31, 2001, during a creative trip to Ellikkala district of Karakalpakstan, during a meeting with hundreds of fans. He was buried in Andijan region. He lived only 46 years, but the poet's poems, which he inherited and surely had a big influence on the growth of Uzbek poetry, may comfort the poet's passing for a poet as diverse as Muhammad Yusuf, with deep sentiments and thoughts. His books such as "Ulugimsan, Vatanim" (2004), "Saylanma" (2007), "Khalk bol, elim" (2009) were published even after his death.

I conclude the position, role and contribution of Muhammad Yusuf in Uzbek poetry with this 4-line poem by Halima Khudoyberdiyeva.

Bir arsloni o'tdi O'zbekning,
Ohi ko'kka etdi O'zbekning,
Quyosh yigla, osmon, aza tut,
Muhammadi ketdi O'zbekning.

A lion passed by an Uzbek,
Uzbek's heart is blue and sighs.
Cry sun, cry sky, and mourn,
Uzbek's Muhammad is gone.
(Halima Khudoyberdiyeva)

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